

D6.1 State of the art

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Executive summary

In this document, HELIX partners have detailed the need for improvements in the field of fasteners and bolts for offshore applications, specifically for offshore wind turbines. First of all, the state of the art on fasteners for offshore applications, steels for fasteners for offshore and corrosion protection has been settled. Accordingly, different strategies have been proposed and will be developed and tested in the HELIX project. On one hand, HELIX will develop, test and provide fasteners able to withstand high applied stresses under harsh environmental conditions typical of large offshore wind turbines. This will be achieved by developing and optimising novel high strength steel grades in qualities 10.9 and 12.9 and new protecting zinc-flake based coatings. On the other hand, HELIX will contribute to unravel how atmospheric and immersed conditions, material composition and microstructure, surface treatment and previous corrosion affect hydrogen embrittlement of high strength steels. HELIX will use advanced characterization techniques as well as traditional techniques to advance in the knowledge of hydrogen absorption in high strength steels under cathodic protection and in atmospheric conditions. This knowledge will not only allow tailoring the steel and coating microstructure to achieve both excellent corrosion protection ability and low risk of hydrogen embrittlement but also influence on policy and practice in the offshore wind sector.

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List of abbreviations

EAC	<i>Environmentally Assisted Cracking</i>
EHE	<i>External Hydrogen Embrittlement</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
HE	<i>Hydrogen Embrittlement</i>
HSS	<i>High Strength Steel</i>
IHE	<i>Internal Hydrogen Embrittlement</i>
LME	<i>Liquid Metal Embrittlement</i>
OWT	<i>Offshore Wind Turbine</i>
SCC	<i>Stress Corrosion Cracking</i>
SCE	<i>Saturated Calomel Electrode</i>
SOA	<i>State Of the Art</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

The European Green Deal plans to accelerate the use of electricity produced from renewables, developing the full potential of Europe's offshore wind energy. To unlock Europe's offshore potential, the number of installed OWT is expected to grow in the coming years. Cost reduction and efficiency are still imperative in this technology and the industry is thus designing larger power generators, up to 20 MW. This trend will lead to larger foundations due to higher mechanical demands combined with harsh environments. Flanged connections are still an integral part of any offshore development with fasteners being the primary means for assembly. Fasteners with diameters over M42 are becoming common and bolts already used can be as high as M72. Therefore, a technical and research effort is needed in the fasteners field to support the ever-increasing size of OWTs.

The HELIX project has been organized around the necessities of the offshore wind industry to increase the reliability of flanged connections. Fastener failures in flanged connections have a service environment, mechanical, human, and material component. The predominant failure mode depends on the application environment and processing history. Brittle fracture of fasteners can occur at low-stress loading. The general model for this kind of fracture, often referred to as the Griffith model, is that a microcrack is nucleated at a particle or defect and then, once it attains a critical size, it serves to concentrate the stress, and propagates rapidly across the sample in a manner consuming little energy [1]. Many types of environments can cause low-energy fracture in steel, but EAC is the most common for subsea applications and marine environment [2]. Essentially all metals used in structural applications are susceptible to hydrogen assisted cracking and embrittlement if the combination of tensile stress and diffusible hydrogen concentration in the material are high enough. The availability of hydrogen in marine applications arises from a combination of sources. Even though hydrogen embrittlement has been found to be the primary cause of bolt failures [2], there is insufficient quantitative understanding of other controlling variables such as the actual loads and the extent of materials degradation by mechanisms such as hydrogen embrittlement in field deployment.

The HELIX project will combine two different material approaches to mitigate the risk of HE of large and bolted connections. The development of new steels with reduced sensitivity to EHE is a route that will lead to the use of safer high strength materials in corrosive environments. The second approach is related to the corrosion protection of the fasteners by novel coatings. Zinc lamellar coatings will be produced with enhanced barrier effect and high corrosion resistance to avoid or limit hydrogen uptake in the steel under harsh environmental conditions. On the other hand, HELIX project will also contribute to unravel the extent of dependency of hydrogen embrittlement on several external variables. Specifically, atmospheric and immersed conditions, material composition and microstructure, surface treatment and previous corrosion are expected to lead to hydrogen embrittlement of the bolt material. In the HELIX project, advanced characterization techniques as well as traditional techniques will be used to advance in the knowledge of hydrogen absorption in HSS under cathodic protection and in atmospheric conditions.

1. State of the Art of Fasteners for offshore wind turbines

1.1 Problem definition

A recent International Energy Agency (IEA) report [3] reveals that the most optimal offshore wind sites could supply more than the total amount of electricity consumed today in the whole World (23,000TWh). Offshore wind energy offers capacity factors comparable to Gas & Coal-fired power plants and is more reliable than solar energy[4]. Over the years, the European Commission (EC) has set key enabling policies for offshore wind and more recently, specific policies for floating wind. In particular, the EC has identified floating substructures for deeper waters as one of the SET-Plan Strategic Targets [3]. Recently, the new European Green Deal [4],[5] plans to accelerate the use of electricity produced from renewables, developing the full potential of Europe’s offshore wind energy. The IEA report [3] already stated that offshore wind is set to play a central role and has the potential to become the largest source of electricity supply (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Offshore wind in the European Union, 2018-2040.

To unlock this potential, several types of offshore structures [6] are already used or in development. Several offshore wind projects in Europe are being developed and installed capacity is expected to increase in the next years. On the other hand, bottom-fixed offshore wind technology still has a limited market potential given its limiting conditions: shallow waters <60m, which for instance means that the Mediterranean, Adriatic and much of the Norwegian shore do not comply [4]. Current trends are pushing towards the deployment of offshore wind technologies in deeper water sites where floating wind turbines could potentially unlock enough electricity to meet the World’s demand in 2040 by 11 times [3]. However, cost reduction and efficiency are still imperative for OWT and therefore, the installation of larger OWT, above 10 MW, is expected in the following years [3],[6]. This trend will lead to larger foundations due to higher mechanical demands for the materials being used (Figure 2).

*Figure 2. Evolution of the largest commercially wind turbines. *Announced expected year of commercial deployments. **Further technology improvements through to 2030 could see bigger turbines sizes of 15-20 MW. Illustration is drawn to scale. Figures in blue indicate the diameter of the swept area.*

The use of bolted connections or links in the offshore wind industry is the main construction technique used since there have been other modes of joints [6]. Furthermore, different foundation designs make use of fasteners and bolts in submerged and atmospheric zones favouring the use of bolted connections. The use of fasteners offer an easy assembly and construction of wind turbines, allowing flanged connections to be an integral part of any offshore developments [6][7]. In offshore conditions, the combined presence of stresses and corrosive environment requires high strength and toughness; good resistance to both corrosion and EAC to meet high reliability and integrity of these systems. As mentioned above, larger wind turbines are being planned and built (Figure 2). These larger turbines will require fasteners with diameters that exceed 42mm (M42). In fact, M42 fasteners are increasingly becoming common and may be the norm in a near future. It is foreseen that sizes of high-strength bolts could be as high as M72 [8] in a near future, since ring flange diameters of 5.5 to 7.0 m and plate thicknesses of 70 mm are not unusual in currently built bottom-fixed foundations.

Nowadays, the materials selection for fasteners in offshore conditions is essentially based on their mechanical properties: yield strength, ultimate strength, toughness, endurance limit, corrosion resistance along with resistance to EAC which includes SCC, HE and corrosion-fatigue. In cathodically protected systems, current alloy steels have given adequate performance from a corrosion point of view but HSS grades are of particular concern due to their lower resistance to cracking. The required fastener sizes is also a challenge for some materials, which may have the combined desired properties, but their applicability is limited due to a lack of uniform through thickness properties as a result of poor hardenability. In addition to these limitations, the economic cost also limits the use of some alloys. In fact, the cost of fasteners in a wind turbine accounts for about 3.5% to 6.0% of the total equipment cost.

Therefore, HELIX will provide fasteners able to withstand high applied stresses under harsh environmental conditions during their whole service life at a reduced economic cost. These new fasteners will support the development of larger foundations to support above 10MW OWT and allow an easy assembly and disassembly of the whole structure.

1.2 Requirements for fastener for offshore wind turbines

HV bolts for OWT are manufactured in accordance with guideline 21 of the German Committee for Steel Construction - DAST-021. DAST-021 continues the specifications of the European Standard EN 14399-4: High strength structural bolting assemblies for preloading - Part 4: System HV - Hexagon bolt and nut assemblies.

The bolts are manufactured by hot forming, thread rolling and heat treatment (quenching and tempering). The mechanical properties are adjusted by a heat treatment process according to the specifications of EN ISO 898-1 for strength class 10.9. In bolts and fasteners of large dimensions ($>M39$), it is necessary to use higher-quality materials to ensure through-tempering of the bolts over the entire cross-section. Beyond the requirements of EN ISO 898-1, an impact energy of at least 27J at a test temperature of -40°C is required for the bolts. It is interesting to note that higher strength classes are not included in DAST-021.

The most common tests defined by DAST-021 are:

- Bolt hardness (cross-section and surface)
- Wedge loading test or tensile test on machined specimen
- Microscopic structure as required in ISO 898-1
- Notch impact force KV/-20 as required in ISO 898-1
- Notch impact force KV/-40 as required by wind industry

The tests to be carried out in the coated assemblies are:

- Friction tests min. in 5 different assemblies one bolt, one nut, two washers for each coating system for M42 HV-PLUS bolts.

After bolt manufacturing, the bolts are hot dip galvanised according to EN ISO 10684: Fasteners - Hot dip galvanised coatings.

For the pre-tensioning of the offshore wind bolts in dimensions $\geq M39$, a preload level is specified which refers to 70% of the yield strength for strength class 10.9. For this purpose, it is necessary to lubricate the HV nuts with a suitable lubricant in such a way that the requirements of DAST-021 for the torque-/preload behaviour can be safely achieved for all connections and thus the assembly on the OWT can be carried out successfully.

To minimize the risk of hydrogen embrittlement, strict regulations for mechanical properties and hot dip galvanization process are given in accordance with DIN EN ISO 10684 and the research results of Deutscher Schraubenverband and Gemeinschaftsausschuss Feuerverzinkung (DSV and GAV):2009. PEINER follows these measures. The following regulations are used during the manufacturing of the bolts:

- Limit of tensile strength and surface hardness (max. 1170 MPa)
- Limit of surface hardness (max. 375 HV0.3)
- Limit of phosphorus and sulfur content of raw material
- Limit of non-metallic inclusions
- No carburization of structure
- No delta-ferrite on surface

Regulations for hot dip galvanizing:

- only use of inhibited acid is allowed
- strict limiting of acid time

2. Steels for offshore wind turbines

The increase of the turbine power leads to higher stressed turbine components, making it necessary to increase their size and/or improve their properties. Although the size increase has been the most common alternative, the components enlargement cannot be indefinitely maintained given the problems associated to their handling, maintenance and transportation [9].

Fasteners for OWT, the parts of the tower on which the investigations of HELIX project are focused, are one of the components subjected to high cyclic loads. Besides, they are also exposed to low temperatures and corrosive environments. The requirements that this type of fasteners must fulfil are specified in the standard ISO 898-1 [10], which defines different fastener classes depending on the strength they must present.

The most common wind fasteners class is 10.9, whose strength is higher than 1,040 MPa and its toughness higher than 27 J at -40°C. The following class is 12.9, with a minimum strength of 1,220 MPa and similar toughness requirements to class 10.9. In both cases, apart from these requirements, 90% of martensitic microstructure in the core of the fastener must be guaranteed, making it necessary to employ steels with a high enough hardenability. Fasteners size has also increased in the last years, passing the maximum metric from 42 mm to 72 mm in the last decade [6]. This has led to the utilization of steels with higher content of elements such as Mn, Ni or Mo to increase the hardenability and consequently assure the required properties in the whole fastener section [11]. Therefore, the most representative grades used in large metrics are 34CrNiMo6 and 30CrNiMo8 in comparison to 32CrB4 or 33MnBCr6 used in the smallest fasteners. This augmentation of the alloying content not only increases the steel price, but also its C footprint [12].

The main goal of the HELIX project in relation to the conventional steels for fasteners of OWT is the design and fabrication of a steel grade which, with a lower alloying content, is able to fulfil all the characteristics required for this application. For this purpose, the reduction of Ni, Cr and Mo content, in comparison to 30CrNiMo8 and 34CrNiMo6, will be faced. This diminution, which will be undertaken keeping in mind the necessity to reach the aforementioned requirements, will provide the following benefits:

- Reduction of the alloying costs and, consequently, the steel price given that the presence of expensive elements will be diminished.
- Considering that the mining processes followed to extract elements such as Ni, Mo, Cr, etc. are very pollutant, the reduction of these elements will lead to a reduced C footprint of the produced steel.
- Finally, the lower alloying content will reduce the dependence on critical elements (i.e. Ni and Mo) whose availability could be in risk in a near future as a consequence of their use in batteries.

3. Hydrogen embrittlement risk in offshore environment

Hydrogen embrittlement is a process resulting in deterioration of mechanical properties due to hydrogen atoms absorbed in the material. Reaching the critical hydrogen concentration in combination with applied stress may lead to the change of fracture behaviour and, in worst cases, cause failure under much lower stress than expected. Several processes are of importance: hydrogen entry from the environment, hydrogen diffusion inside the metal and hydrogen trapping at structural defects. Hydrogen entry depends on the state of the material surface and environmental conditions, while diffusion and trapping are strongly affected by steel microstructure.

There are two types of HE: internal and environmental. Internal HE is caused by residual hydrogen from steelmaking or processing, while environmental or external HE is a result of hydrogen absorption from external sources, as an exposure to gaseous hydrogen at elevated temperature and corrosion. Hydrogen can be absorbed during steel fabrication steps such as pickling, cleaning, phosphating, or electroplating. Hydrogen evolution reaction is the main cathodic reaction during these procedures. A recommended or even mandatory step after steel production is the hydrogen content reduction by baking at temperature about 200°C. Most of absorbed hydrogen diffuses out to the atmosphere, while residual hydrogen is homogeneously redistributed in the bulk material.

Hydrogen can enter steel from gas and from aqueous environment. While the gaseous source is not relevant for offshore environment, hydrogen entry from solution or thin electrolyte layer should be considered. The primary step of hydrogen entry process from aqueous environments is hydrogen reduction reaction, as hydrogen is present in the solution as hydrogen ions, see Figure 3. The electrochemical adsorption of hydrogen in solution, better known as the “Hydrogen Evolution Reaction” (HER), involves three basic steps: 1) the electro-adsorption/ desorption of hydrogen (Volmer’s reaction) electro-dissociation/ combination of hydrogen (Heyrovsky’s reaction) and 3) chemical desorption (Tafel’s reaction). This Volmer reaction (Eq. 1) competes with Heyrovsky (Eq. 2) and Tafel (Eq. 3) desorption reactions [13], where hydrogen molecules form and under suitable conditions can leave the surface as gas. The recombination process can be inhibited and hydrogen entry into metal thus promoted by recombination poisons such as arsenic, antimony, sulfide, thiourea, etc., which block active centres of the metal by adsorbing on them [14].

Whereas a part of adsorbed hydrogen atoms recombines into molecules and desorbs out, a part of the adsorbed hydrogen enters into the metal by reaction

Hydrogen entry depends on the surface coverage with atomic hydrogen, which may be affected by temperature and state of the surface, as the presence of other species

[15]. It also depends on the surface potential. Solubility of hydrogen from aqueous solution is proportional to square root of current density [16].

Figure 3: *Main hydrogen evolution reactions at the surface of a metal from aqueous and gaseous media: (1) adsorption, (2) surface migration, (4) subsurface absorption [(4') direct absorption], (5) bulk diffusion and trapping, (6) molecular recombination.*

When hydrogen is absorbed into a material, hydrogen diffusion, trapping and de-trapping processes take place. Hydrogen transport through a material proceeds by interstitial jumps in the lattice, short circuit paths as grain boundaries or by moving dislocations [17]. While a part of absorbed hydrogen diffuses through the material and escapes it, some hydrogen atoms can be immobilized in the material structure. This phenomenon is described as hydrogen trapping. Voids, dislocation, grain boundaries, carbide interfaces, and impurities may act as trapping sites. The trapping sites have different binding energy and are commonly categorized into two groups: reversible and irreversible. Irreversible trapping sites have high trap activation energy, thus, the probability of hydrogen de-trapping is low. Reversible trapping sites have lower energy and can release trapped hydrogen atoms. High-angle grain boundaries, incoherent precipitates, and nonmetallic inclusions are examples of irreversible trapping sites, while dislocations, low-angle grain boundaries or microvoids are considered as reversible traps. It is considered that homogeneously distributed irreversible trapping sites may increase resistance to hydrogen induced cracking, as they tightly bond hydrogen atoms [18][19]. However, it works only if a small amount of hydrogen is absorbed and irreversible traps are free to catch it. On the contrary, the reversible trapping sites can be detrimental, as they provide temporary reservoir for hydrogen. When the external stress is applied to the material, hydrogen can be released from reversible traps to the lattice and diffuse to the high stress field [20],[21]. It was reported that dislocations are the main reversible trapping sites controlling the mobility of hydrogen due to their lowest binding energy among other trapping sites [22]. Thus, the transport of hydrogen in metals is affected by the presence of microstructural defects.

3.1 Corrosion as a source of hydrogen

In offshore applications, corrosion under atmospheric and immersion conditions should be considered. In the case of hydrogen entry linked to corrosion of steel, we assume presence of a thin water layer on the steel surface under atmospheric conditions or bulk aqueous solution under immersion in water electrolyte. Corrosion on the metal surface is a complex electrochemical process which can be described by simplified anodic and cathodic reactions. Iron dissolution reaction, i.e. the anodic reaction, can be written in as

and the corresponding cathodic reactions may be oxygen reduction at neutral pH of the water solution (6) or hydrogen ion reduction at lower pH (7):

Hydrogen entry into steel is often associated with hydrolysis reactions, where hydrogen ions are produced. Hydrolysis of ferrous and ferritic ions is accompanied by proton liberation and a decrease in pH to about 3 [23]. Hydrolysis accompanies also formation of corrosion products, Fe^{2+} being converted to FeOH^+ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$. Oxidation of ferrous ions is assumed to be a further source of acidity due to hydrogen ion production.

Further, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and FeOH^+ are oxidized to iron oxyhydroxides FeOOH and additional hydrogen ions are produced:

Hydrogen ions produced via reactions (8-12) might be reduced on the surface and partly absorbed into the steel. Hydrolysis reactions are enhanced beneath and within corrosion products layers. Thus, it can be expected that hydrogen entry increases with a progress of corrosion. However, formation of corrosion products after prolonged exposure time was reported to limit hydrogen entry [24][26]. It is probable that the formation of initial corrosion products enhances hydrogen generation and entry due to the hydrolysis, whereas stable corrosion product layers cause reduction of the available steel surface area for the hydrogen reduction reaction and suppress the hydrogen entry process.

Hydrogen entry linked to corrosion occurs mainly when the pH at the metal/corrosion products interface and corrosion potential reach low values. Under atmospheric corrosion conditions, a decrease in pH is expected when corrosion products are present on the metal surface or pollutants as SO_2 are in the environment [26]. Hydrolysis of

SO₂ and formation of ferrous sulphate can be another process of hydrogen ion evolution:

Presence of CO₂ can also lead to an increased hydrogen uptake, when CO₂ is dissolved in water and carbonic acid is formed. The carbonic acid dissociates resulting in an increase in the hydrogen proton concentration, i.e., a drop in pH, and the cathodic reaction is promoted.

Generation and absorption of hydrogen in steels in atmospheric marine environment was reported in several studies [27]-[30]. For steels exposed to marine atmosphere, corrosion condition is very severe. High humidity, salinity, long wetting times are factors which promote corrosion and, subsequently, hydrogen entry [26]. Steels immersed in seawater were reported to suffer from more pronounced hydrogen embrittlement compared to atmospheric marine exposure [29]. Moreover, when steel is coated, hydrogen entry can be further enhanced.

3.2 Effect of zinc coating

Sacrificial coatings, such as zinc-based coatings, is one of the most popular solutions to protect steel from corrosion. Coated steels are used in marine environments. However, occurrence of defects in the coatings should be considered in view of hydrogen entry. Galvanic coupling between steel substrate in a defect and zinc coating polarizes steel to less noble corrosion potential. The shift of corrosion potential in negative direction occurs when steel is coupled with zinc [31]. It is known that hydrogen evolution reaction is enhanced at more negative corrosion potential values [32]. Thus, hydrogen formation and absorption are expected to be accelerated by galvanic coupling between zinc coating and steel substrate.

Several studies indicated that the effect of galvanic coupling on hydrogen formation and entry is significant if steel is immersed in salt solution. Scharf et al. [33] demonstrated that hydrogen uptake into zinc coating in contact with steel substrate at cut edges is high and independent of the solution pH, while sufficient hydrogen absorption into bare steel occurs only at low pH value. Kitahara et al. [34] also revealed a larger amount of absorbed hydrogen when zinc was coupled with iron compared to hydrogen absorbed due to steel corrosion. Moreover, hydrogen uptake into zinc coated steel is expected to be more localized due to local occurrence of defects in the coating, whereas hydrogen absorption into bare steel may be considered as more uniform [35]. Higher local hydrogen concentration might accelerate the negative effect of the absorbed hydrogen. Nazarov et al. [35] confirmed a high hydrogen entry from galvanized steel with a defect exposed to an aqueous salt solution.

On the other hand, the effect of zinc-steel galvanic coupling can be inhibited by deposition of zinc corrosion products on the steel surface [36][38]. It was reported that a shift of free corrosion potential to noble values due to formation of zinc corrosion products led to a significant decrease in hydrogen entry [32]. Otherwise, under

atmospheric conditions, zinc corrosion products might keep moisture for longer time compared to iron corrosion products causing prolonged hydrogen uptake during drying.

3.3 Hydrogen entry due to cathodic protection

Cathodic protection is used to control the corrosion rate of steel in sea water. Otherwise, polarisation of steel in cathodic direction can lead to hydrogen formation and entry to the steel. Banerjee et al. [39] reported that there is already a risk of hydrogen embrittlement at potentials beyond -800 mV (SCE). Liang et al. [40] observed obvious hydrogen embrittlement at potential -900 mV (SCE). More protective potentials would have caused higher level of hydrogen uptake [41]. Thus, a balance between corrosion protection and low probability of hydrogen entry should be kept. If the potential in the range -770 to -790 mV (SCE) is used, adequate corrosion protection with low risk of hydrogen embrittlement is ensured [42]. Cathodic overprotection in seawater generates high amount of hydrogen, which can be sufficient to cause hydrogen embrittlement of HSS [41].

Hydrogen entry into steel under cathodic protection depends not only on the applied potential. Hydrogen embrittlement becomes more pronounced with increasing cathodic current density in sea water, which correlates with increasing diffusible hydrogen concentration [43]. Acidity of the solution might play a role, as more pronounced embrittlement effect was reported for steels cathodically charged in acidic salt solution compared to neutral one [44]. Moreover, in the presence of sulfate reducing bacteria in sea water, higher hydrogen uptake to steels under cathodic protection was observed owing to production of H_2S , decrease in pH and increase in the polarization current due to prevention of the cathodic deposits formation [45],[46]. Thus, hydrogen uptake into steels under cathodic protection should be studied more in detail for particular conditions and effect of hydrogen in concentrations produced under such conditions on fracture behavior of steels should be evaluated.

4. Corrosion protection of fasteners for offshore wind turbines

Bolts in OWT are exposed to different environments depending on the installation zone: (a) atmospheric zone, (b) tidal zone, (c) submerged zone and (d) buried or mud/sediment zone. Thus, different requirements for fastener material are demanded depending on the exposure zones as well as the service conditions. There is a need to ensure that corrosion and other degradation mechanisms can be avoided. For the atmospheric zone, general corrosion, localized corrosion and galvanic corrosion will be the most critical. However, the use of HSS fasteners, which are known to be prone to hydrogen embrittlement (HE), in the atmospheric zone makes EAC and corrosion-fatigue also a risk. For submerged zones, the bolts are mostly cathodically protected and the main degradation mechanisms are fatigue, corrosion-fatigue and HE.

To reduce the possibilities of the above-mentioned failure mechanisms, surface coatings are usually applied to protect the fasteners. Surface coatings on fasteners are multifunctional combining corrosion resistance, scratch resistance and excellent

frictional characteristics to facilitate their insertion during assembly. Also, both coating material and deposition process are expected to be environmentally friendly and cost effective.

For steel fasteners in the offshore industry often hot dip galvanizing is used. The hot dip galvanization leads to a cathodic protective surface on the steel. This coating has a thickness around 60 to 100 μm . European research on hot dip galvanization has been carried out to reduce steel corrosion [6][8]. Another approved coating solution for offshore fasteners are zinc flake systems [47][48]. For similar anti-corrosion performance, those systems are usually much thinner (compared to hot dip galvanized surfaces and consists typically out of a basecoat and a topcoat. The basecoat, which contains zinc flakes, delivers the cathodic corrosion protection while the topcoat gives the system good chemical resistance, defined friction properties and increased corrosion protection and galvanic effect. Zinc flake systems are approved in several specifications throughout the automotive, wind and offshore industries. In these fields, they deliver very good corrosion protection since many years [47]-[49].

For example, zinc flake systems received the Germanischer Lloyd's certificate for use on standard bolts of sizes M24 to M48 for onshore and offshore wind turbines. It was categorised as C5 high according to ISO 12944-6. At the same time, a long-term experiment began to investigate the influence of the offshore climate on different coating systems. For this test coated M24 bolts were moved to the FINO 2 research platform in the baltic sea at 12.5 and 25 metres above sea level and are being exposed there to all prevailing external influences since 2013.

The efficacy of these systems has also been proved by a study conducted by the Federal Institute of Materials Research and Testing together with the German Institute of Civil Engineering. The study included exposing the coating systems to an outside weathering test of 36 months in urban and marine climates and comparing the corrosion resistance of a DELTA-MKS® system with that of a hot-dip galvanized system.

One of the main drawbacks for the application of hot dip galvanization on large diameter fasteners of 12.9 steel grade is their tendency to LME or HE during the manufacturing process and service life, as shown above. This can limit the use of this steel grade in offshore structures.

Novel zinc flake systems could be used for improved corrosion protection and EAC avoidance in fasteners for offshore application. Therefore, the Helix project will develop customized basecoats and topcoats that together meet offshore corrosion requirements and prevent HE. This can be achieved by an optimal combination of basecoat and topcoat and additionally optimized by the best possible application parameters of the layers such as pre-treatment, layer weight and curing conditions.

5. Problem encountered and proposed approach

5.1 Environmental solicitations on bolted connections

The use of HSS bolted connections or links in the offshore wind industry has steeply risen due to failings in other modes of joints [6], but also due to the increase of different foundation designs that make use of fasteners and bolts in submerged and

atmospheric zones. For ease of assembly and construction, flanged connections are still an integral part of any offshore developments [6][7] with fasteners being the primary means for assembly. The combined presence of stresses and corrosive environment requires high strength and toughness; good resistance to both corrosion and EAC in order to meet high reliability and integrity of these systems. As larger wind turbines are being built (see **Error! No s'ha trobat l'origen de la referència.**), larger diameter and higher strength steels fasteners are being used. Fasteners with diameters that exceed 48mm (M48) are increasingly becoming common and may be the norm in a near future. In fact, the sizes of the high-strength bolts used can be as high as M72 [8], since ring flange diameters of 5.5 to 7.0 m and plate thicknesses of 70 mm are not unusual in currently built bottom-fixed foundations.

Due to the harsh service demands on fasteners in OWT, the materials selection is essentially based on their mechanical properties: yield strength, ultimate strength, toughness, endurance limit, corrosion resistance along with resistance to EAC which includes SCC, HE and corrosion-fatigue. While alloy steels had given adequate performance from a corrosion point of view in cathodically protected systems, their resistance to cracking has been a major concern particularly for the HSS grades [41],[46]. Although some materials may have the combined desired properties, their applicability is limited due to size limitation or lack of uniform through thickness properties as a result of inadequate hardenability. In addition to these limitations, high cost is another factor that limits the use of some alloys. In fact, the cost of fasteners in a wind turbine accounts for about 3.5% to 6.0% of the total equipment cost.

5.2 The risk of hydrogen embrittlement

It is recognised that HSS are prone to HE and their resistance decreases with the increase in strength [50][56]. The resistance of these materials is generally expressed in terms of hardness limit above which the material is not recommended for use in the specific environment or in terms of HE threshold stress intensity factors. HE phenomenon in HSS may lead to brittle fracture [52][54][55]. Therefore, HE is a common serious problem in steels and specifically, in fasteners manufactured in HSS [56]-[58].

Hydrogen absorbed as mentioned in section 3, may be located in interstitial sites. This hydrogen is called “diffusible hydrogen” and presents the lowest activation energy, so it is able to easily diffuse into the material. When the material is exposed to external stresses or residual stresses, diffusible hydrogen will diffuse to zones of high stress, resulting in HE.

HE (IHE or EHE) cracking can occur when the following three factors have been satisfied simultaneously.

- a) Hydrogen concentration (H_c) above a threshold level, H_{Th}
- b) Sustained tensile stress (σ) above a threshold level, σ_{Th}
- c) Material's susceptibility (S) to HE cracking above a threshold level, S_{Th}

H_{Th} , σ_{Th} , and S_{Th} are interdependent. That is, the higher the S_{Th} , the lower the H_{Th} , σ_{Th} , or both. H_{Th} may range from much less than one to several wppm (parts per million by

weight) and pretension stress, σ , is set by design. This would leave S_{Th} as a practical tool to control IHE and EHE cracking.

To reduce the S_{Th} of a HSS to HE, only the optimisation of the microstructure leaves room for improvement [59]. The purity of the steel is a critical factor [60]. The microstructure phases also have a major influence due to differences in their levels of H solubility and hardness. Precipitates: chemical composition and morphology also affect fracture behaviour [61][62]. Steel composition can also reduce HE susceptibility by adding alloying elements which form high activation energy sites [59][59]. Using these “hydrogen traps”, it is possible to develop HSS without increasing the risk of HE.

The use of Zn coatings further enhances the HE susceptibility, as mentioned in section 3. For example, the EHE threshold of black and galvanized 4140 steel bars was determined according to ASTM E1681 [50]. The EHE threshold labelled as K_{sc} is shown in Figure 4 for quenched and tempered 4140 steel bars with hardness in the range 33-49HRC slowly loaded in 3.5% NaCl solution. As shown in this graph, the EHE thresholds of galvanized steel are significantly lower than that of bare steel, owing to the increased H activity resulting from galvanic corrosion of the coating. Furthermore, EHE threshold of galvanized steel shows a notable decrease from 58 to 20ksi.in^{1/2} as the hardness increases from 30 to 40 HRC. This has been reflected in standards ASTM A490 and A354 Grade BD that have a warning statement about the danger of HE cracking when structural bolts are hot dip galvanized. Similar warnings may be found elsewhere, for example in ASTM A143, ASTM B633, ASTM B850, ASTM F2329 and FHWA-SA-91-031. A careful evaluation is also needed particularly for large diameter fasteners in case of the lower hardenability of the HSS grade used. Unfortunately, the perception of S_{Th} is different from one technical committee to another, tasked with establishing industry standards/specifications for bolting. The maximum hardness below which post-plating hydrogen bake-out heat treatment is not required for avoiding IHE cracking, varies from 31 to 39HRC depending on the standard. This hardness range is too wide to be trustworthy if only for the prevention of IHE cracking. The 31HRC maximum requirement can prevent both IHE and EHE cracking. However, some organizations are concerned mostly about IHE and very little about EHE cracking in immersion services. ASTM F1941 states: “Through hardened fasteners with a specified maximum hardness of 39HRC and below has a low susceptibility to HE and do not require baking”. This may be true of IHE but it is misleading because HE includes both IHE and EHE.

This confusing situation exists because the hardness requirements for avoiding IHE/EHE cracking are established based more on experience than on scientific data. Few recognize that the precautions to prevent IHE cracking, such as post-plating H bake-out heat treatment, cannot prevent EHE cracking, especially in immersion services. Most low alloy steel bolting material specifications would need to differentiate the susceptibility to IHE from EHE.

The most common source of hydrogen in offshore service environment are linked to cathodic protection systems or free corrosion. Under atmospheric corrosion conditions, it has been shown that H can be generated either by galvanic coupling with zinc coating or by local corrosion of the steel [29]. In the case of zinc coated steel, any defect in the zinc layer might become the source of hydrogen entry in the presence of a water film. As a consequence, EHE is prone to occur in offshore environment for sensitive

steels (with tensile strength over 1000MPa) when hydrogen uptake by corrosion is coupled with residual or applied stress.

For zinc lamellar coatings, water uptake in the coating could also contribute to the production of hydrogen at the surface of the steel. But zinc flake coatings offer a good solution to EHE. After an initial activation stage, galvanic coupling among the zinc present in the coating and the steel takes place and could lead to EHE. However, zinc corrosion products are formed providing a long-term barrier protection period. In this stage, corrosive consumption of zinc particles continues but fails to generate a sufficient galvanic effect, thus avoiding EHE. Although a lot of research progress has been achieved regarding zinc-rich primer performance, better anticorrosion properties, and specifically more durable coatings, can be achieved by tailoring the composition and controlling the electron flow processes.

Figure 4: EHE Tests [50]. Open circles - Fast fracture for all surfaces; Crosses - no coating; Black circles - hot-dip 55%Al-Zn; Blue triangles - hot-dip Zn; Yellow squares - electroplated and baked Zn.

5.3 Mitigating hydrogen embrittlement

Two different approaches will be combined in the project to mitigate the risk of HE of large and bolted connections. First, new steels will be developed with reduced sensitivity to EHE. Then, zinc lamellar coatings will be produced with enhanced barrier effect and high corrosion resistance to avoid or limit hydrogen uptake in the steel under harsh environmental conditions. Therefore, fasteners that can withstand high applied stresses under harsh environmental conditions during their whole service life

at a reduced economic cost will be developed. These new fasteners will support the development of larger foundations to support above 10 MW OWT and allow an easy assembly and disassembly of the whole structure.

5.3.1 Development of new steel grades

The knowledge exists today to optimize the design of connector alloys with improved intrinsic resistance to hydrogen embrittlement. Furthermore, the developed steel grades will need to satisfy the materials property requirements. Alloys may be designed to (1) resist hydrogen production and uptake, (2) trap and sequester hydrogen away from fracture sites like grain boundaries, (3) provide improved fracture resistance (or a higher critical hydrogen concentration). A recent survey of possible alternative fastener alloys using off-the-shelf materials was compiled by Raymond [63]. In this case, empirical screening was used. Precipitation aged hardened variants of Cu-Ni and Ni-Cr-Mo alloys were explored and found to exceed the hydrogen resistance of steels when subjected to cathodic polarization.

Amongst the measures available for intrinsic improvements in alloy resistance are segregation control of deleterious elements like sulphur and phosphor [64], trap control, alloy cleanliness and other measures to increase resistance to cracking for a given hydrogen level [65]. In some materials, boron has been added as a bond promoter. A series of benign traps such as vanadium or molybdenum carbides can be engineered to slow diffusion. The trap binding energy needs to be strong enough so that hydrogen is not supplied to the stress field of the crack tip [59].

In offshore conditions, continual hydrogen production can lead to saturation of such traps and subsequent EAC. Different measures may be utilized to decrease hydrogen production, uptake and trapping with the goal of bringing about a lower diffusible hydrogen content. It should be noted that trap site control is complex and may not be feasible in open systems allowing continual hydrogen production and uptake where trap filling and saturation may occur.

Presently, M64 (or larger metrics) fasteners with 12.9 steel grade quality are not produced due to risks of LME during hot-dip galvanizing or HE risk during service. Thus, high HE resistance 12.9 steel grade quality needs to be developed to be able to build large offshore wind structures. Therefore, the basis for improved HSS with high toughness and resistance to HE at a lower economic cost proposed in HELIX relies on the optimization of the chemical composition and the steel manufacturing process:

a) Chemical composition: The optimized steels are Cr-Ni-B grades with a balanced alloying to increase hardenability and minimize the alloying cost. The steel composition will reduce traditional expensive alloying elements, such as Mo and Ni, with regard to the steel grades currently used, but reinforcing the required hardenability by microalloying with Ti and B to achieve $\geq 90\%$ martensite at the fastener core in large diameters. Microprecipitates also create H-trapping sites, which mitigate HE phenomenon. Steelmaking control of the S and P contents helps to maximize the toughness at low temperature. Steels with two different chemical compositions will be produced at laboratory scale. The one showing the best performance in corrosion

resistance, mechanical properties (LIST, CLT) and hardenability will be used in the project.

b) Steel manufacturing process: The improvement of the manufacturing process will focus on the optimization of the main parameters of the secondary metallurgy, continuous casting and heat treatment to improve the cast homogenization and obtain a fine distribution of microprecipitates. Hot rolling and hot forging parameters must be kept in a certain range to avoid microprecipitate coarsening. Quenching and tempering parameters (austenization, tempering temperatures, times) will also be optimized to obtain tough tempered martensite, leading to high toughness and high HE-resistant steels.

5.3.2 Development of new coatings

The principle of the corrosion protection system based on zinc flakes coating film is shown in Figure 5. A specific top-coat that decrease the friction coefficient or further improve the corrosion protection of the system can be sometimes required to fulfil the requirements of the final application. Self-lubricant systems are also available in the market.

Figure 5: Principle of corrosion protection system using zinc flakes.

The corrosion protection for zinc flakes coating films is based on the barrier effect of the coating and the local cathodic protection of the steel substrate by the zinc flakes. Therefore, in order to achieve high corrosion resistance, corrosion products developed from the coating must play an important role, just as with metallic zinc coatings. Indeed, Zn/Al flake coating films can form and maintain alkaline zinc chloro-hydroxides as corrosion products in a corrosive environment with chlorides [66]. In ideal condition, a thin protective layer of zinc chloro-hydroxide is obtained at the surface of the coating quickly after exposure to the corrosion environment, limiting further oxidation of the flakes. The addition of the aluminium flakes acts to improve the barrier properties of the coating and may also mitigate the corrosion rate of the zinc [67].

During exposure of zinc flakes to corrosion environment, water/moisture uptake can occur in the coating. The distribution and shape of the flakes in the coating is crucial for the kinetics of the water absorption. After incubation time, an electrolyte is obtained, and galvanic coupling of zinc/aluminium flakes and steel takes place. The efficiency of the cathodic protection is affected by the electrical conductivity of the coating and the possibility of insulation of the flakes by corrosion products. Factors

that mitigate the zinc corrosion rate will also decrease the self-healing capability of the system.

When galvanic coupling is operating, the electrochemical degradation of zinc flakes can be high because of the high conductivity of the flakes and the unfavourable ratio of surface to volume. The coating formulation is therefore required to reduce this degradation rate by means of the barrier effect of the appropriate used binder system. A long-lasting cathodic protection can be also achieved by optimizing the electrical contacts of the zinc flakes among each other by selecting a suitable size distribution so that the complete zinc content of the protective layer may act as galvanic anode.

Coatings anodic to the substrate metal may lead to HE due to cathodic polarization of the metal in defects. By changing the combination of basecoat and topcoat characteristics, the performance of the coatings can be adapted and the risk of HE limited. The corrosion behaviour of the basecoat depends on the morphology and composition of the zinc flakes and the nature of the binder. The basecoat can act as a passive layer by building a barrier or as an active layer by sacrificing the zinc to protect the steel. Reducing or increasing this cathodic corrosion protection of the zinc flakes has an impact on the corrosion performance but also on the HE phenomenon.

The choice of the right topcoat also plays an important role. Topcoats can be inorganic and porous or organic and denser. The right combination of basecoat and topcoat for the surrounding corrosive atmosphere will be studied. The developed coatings will be a new surface coating technology that can be applied to HSS fasteners with the following advantages:

1. Superior corrosion resistance: The thickness of the film will be only 20 to 40µm, but its rust-preventing effect will be higher than that of traditional electro-galvanizing, hot-dip galvanizing or organic coatings.
2. Low to non-HE phenomenon: The coatings will not produce any hydrogen during the application process and low to no hydrogen production in service even in harsh environments.
3. High heat resistance: Heat-resistant temperature will be above 300°C.
4. Lower environmental impact: During the whole production process and coating procedure, the zinc flake-based coatings lower the environmental impact with no polluted wastewater nor waste gas.
5. Able to be used on 12.9 steel grade fasteners: the coatings will provide the required corrosion protection without having HE, nor LME as could be in the case of the hot dip galvanization. Without any risk of IHE due to the process with mechanical pre-treatment, and a reduction of the EHE due to the environment and the coating consumption, the zinc flake systems and particularly the HELIX zinc flakes innovations should be an answer for the coating of 12.9 new steel fasteners.

6. Outcomes and progress beyond the state of the art

HELIX objectives target three industrial sectors of large importance in terms of employment, contribution to EU Gross Domestic Product, innovation and R&D

investment and capacity to address systemic crisis such as climate change and the recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic: Steel industry, Energy sector and Chemical/Coatings sector. The outcomes of the project will reach well-beyond these sectors, the specific novel products and their current markets. They will also contribute to enhance the implementation of clean-energy generation, increase and maintain jobs, reduce CO₂ emissions, enhance circular economy, push the EU to the forefront in the renewable sector and strengthen the European industry value-chain.

6.1 Innovative content of the proposal and progress beyond the state of the art

The innovative value of HELIX is of incremental nature but will have high implications for the offshore sector. The progress beyond the state of the art and the most innovative content in HELIX is summarized below:

- **Innovations in HSS with high toughness and resistance to HE:** The basis for improved HSS with high toughness and resistance to HE at a lower economic cost relies on the optimization of the chemical composition and the steel manufacturing process:

a) **Chemical composition:** The optimized steels are Cr-Ni-B grades with a balanced alloying to increase hardenability and minimize the alloying cost. The steel composition will reduce traditional expensive alloying elements, such as Mo and Ni, with regard to the steel grades currently used, but reinforcing the required hardenability by microalloying with Ti and B to achieve $\geq 90\%$ martensite at the fastener core in large diameters. Microprecipitates also create H-trapping sites, which mitigate HE phenomenon. Steelmaking control of the S and P contents helps to maximize the toughness at low temperature. Steels with two different chemical compositions will be produced at laboratory scale. The one showing the best performance in corrosion resistance, mechanical properties (LIST, CLT) and hardenability will be used in the project.

b) **Steel manufacturing process:** The improvement of the manufacturing process will focus on the optimization of the main parameters of the secondary metallurgy, continuous casting and heat treatment to improve the cast homogenization and obtain a fine distribution of microprecipitates. Hot rolling and hot forging parameters must be kept in a certain range to avoid microprecipitate coarsening. Quenching and tempering parameters (austenization, tempering temperatures, times) will also be optimized to obtain tough tempered martensite, leading to high toughness and high HE-resistant steels.

- **Innovation in coating development:** Dörken is developing zinc flake systems since 1980. By changing the combination of basecoat and topcoat characteristics, the performance of the coatings can be adapted.

The corrosion behaviour of the basecoat depends on the morphology and composition of the zinc flakes and the nature of the binder. The basecoat can act as a passive layer by building a barrier or as an active layer by sacrificing the zinc to protect the steel. Reducing or increasing this cathodic corrosion protection of the zinc flakes has an impact on the corrosion performance but also on the HE phenomenon.

The choice of the right topcoat also plays an important role. Topcoats can be inorganic and porous or organic and denser. Finding the right combination of basecoat and topcoat for the surrounding corrosive atmosphere is one key goal to achieve in HELIX.

The coatings developed in *HELIX* will be a new surface coating technology that can be applied to HSS fasteners and its advantages will be:

1. *Superior corrosion resistance*: The thickness of the film will be only 20 to 40µm, but its rust-preventing effect will be higher than that of traditional electro-galvanizing, hot-dip galvanizing or organic coatings.
2. *Low to non-HE phenomenon*: The coatings will not produce any hydrogen during the application process and low to no hydrogen production in service even in harsh environments.
3. *High heat resistance*: Heat-resistant temperature will be above 300°C.
4. *Lower environmental impact*: During the whole production process and coating procedure, the zinc-flake based coatings lower the environmental impact with no polluted wastewater nor waste gas.
5. *Able to be used on 12.9 steel grade fasteners*: the coatings will provide the required corrosion protection without having HE, nor LME as could be in the case of the hot dip galvanization. Without any risk of IHE due to the process with mechanical pre-treatment, and a reduction of the EHE due to the environment and the coating consumption, the zinc flake systems and particularly the *HELIX* zinc flakes innovations should be an answer for the coating of 12.9 new steel fasteners.

- ***Better understanding of interaction between steel, coating and service environment in HE phenomenon:***

It is well known that HSSs with tensile strength over 1GPa are sensitive to HE. There are two main hydrogen sources, which cause HE, the manufacturing process and service life. The former source includes acid pickling, surface treatment, welding and other operations. They are now well recognized and proper manufacturing procedures can reduce the risk of IHE. However, the latter source is harder to control and the available knowledge is insufficient. For subsea applications under cathodic protection, hydrogen is produced by the cathodic reduction of water at the surface of the protected steel. Under atmospheric corrosion conditions, hydrogen can be generated during corrosion by H⁺ reduction accompanying metal oxidation. It is still unclear how exposure conditions, material composition and microstructure, surface treatment and previous corrosion affect the process. There is even less known about these effects under atmospheric corrosion conditions, where experiments are significantly more demanding than in immersion due to lower hydrogen formation. In this project, strong attention will be paid to several of these unsolved questions.

Concerning subsea conditions, the activity of hydrogen will be characterized for each steel using electrochemical permeation test. Then, the sensitivity of the steels will be assessed under representative charging conditions using various mechanical tests (constant load test, incremental step load test, fatigue and fracture mechanics). In particular, some tests will be conducted on real bolt assemblies or using stress concentrators representative of real size bolts used in service. This way, the risks of HE under service conditions will be fully characterized and could be extended for larger bolting. Moreover, to anticipate the particular conditions that could be faced in the tidal zone on coated bolting, with alternance of immersion and atmospheric conditions, the effect from the cathodic protection on the physical properties of the coating (e.g. cathodic disbondment) and risks of HE during full immersion tests will be evaluated using similar experimental procedure as for bare steel.

For atmospheric conditions, coatings separating metal from environment can be considered as efficient tools for mitigation of HE. Coatings able to provide cathodic protection of substrate metal can enhance the risk of HE due to cathodic polarization of the metal in defects in the presence of thin water film. This can be the case of zinc coatings or even organic-metallic coatings with zinc flakes. Using advanced techniques such as in situ SKP and Computed Tomography (CT), as well as traditional techniques modified for improved sensitivity under atmospheric conditions such as Slow Strain Rate Tests (SSRT), Constant Load Tests (CLT), corrosion fatigue testing etc., the effect of different coating parameters on hydrogen insertion and HE will be studied (see section 3.1 and FORM B2 for details on the methods and techniques used to gain new knowledge). In particular, it will be investigated if steel corrosion protection by the cathodic effect of zinc flakes is inherently linked to increased risk of HE. It is believed that the coating structure (primer and topcoat composition and permeability) can be tailored in order to achieve both excellent corrosion protection and low HE risk. It is expected that HELIX will provide new insights into the mechanism behind both factors and identify properties controlling each of them. This way, recommendations could be made to minimize the risks of hydrogen generation by corrosion of the protective coating and the subsequent HE phenomenon. Such results will be generally applicable for all types of organic coatings and not only those studied in this project.

In the second step, when the optimal coating system will be combined with reference and newly developed HSS grades, the study will focus on the interaction between a coating and HSS with different compositions and microstructures. It is believed that steel microstructure affects the tendency to HE, but there is still not enough data to quantify it. In HELIX, the HSSs will be thoroughly characterized, which will allow for interpretation of data on hydrogen entry and HE.

In lesser extent, the effect of exposure conditions, i.e. type of service environment and natural cyclic changes, on HE will also be investigated. It will be allowed especially by in situ techniques such as SKP and hydrogen permeation cell. Finally, it is expected that corrosion products formed on the metal surface also play a role in hydrogen formation and entry characteristics. Some experiments will be performed in order to assess the importance of the surface state on the HE risk. From all these experiments, the critical phases and climatic conditions that could lead to HE will be highlighted to anticipate the risks of failure under service conditions.

Finally, the laboratory scale experiments will be compared to full scale assemblies tested under real service environments to validate the resistance to HE of the selected system(s).

6.2 Main project deliverables and industrial benefits

The offshore wind industry is facing an increasing demand to enlarge the size of new turbines but also to keep the costs as low as possible. The ever-increasing size introduces new demands in terms of load to the structure. The need for high dimension fasteners in the sector is just around the corner and therefore, the steel industry seeks to offer new steel solutions at a competitive cost. The presently used steel grades are highly alloyed and despite their high performance, they are not cost-efficient. Furthermore, the harsh environments suffered by offshore structures requires the use

of steels with high HE resistance and coatings that do not accelerate hydrogen uptake. Thus, the main deliverables and industrial benefits of HELIX will be:

- (1) Optimized steel grades with high hardenability, HE resistance and toughness.
- (2) Demonstration of the feasibility of high dimension fasteners with lower cost and high performance in real offshore environment.
- (3) Novel zinc-flakes-based coatings with high corrosion resistance and low to no hydrogen production.
- (4) Advances in the understanding of HE in HSS in offshore environments.
- (5) Experimental results to predict the material behaviour in real service life.
- (6) Guidelines for the offshore wind industry for the correct protection of fasteners.

Furthermore, HELIX will contribute to the Action Plan on the competitiveness of the steel sector launched in 2013 by the EC to help the steel industry return to pre-crisis production levels [http://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/raw-materials/industries/metals/steel/index_en.htm]. In particular, HELIX solutions will have the following major impacts in the steel sector:

- 1) Increase steel application competitiveness
- 2) Increase the amount of steel produced
- 3) Better understanding of EHE phenomenon in HSS
- 4) Cost reduction and new designs for OWT, leading to more steel demand

It is also worth noting that the HELIX findings, developments and industrial benefits have high replicability and transferability beyond the offshore wind sector. If the overall concept of tailoring the corrosion protection properties and HE resistance of coated HSS joining materials is proved correct, it will open path for further development of similar wide-scale solutions in the offshore industry, construction, heavy equipment, Oil & Gas (O&G) as well as chemical industry. For example, novel floating solar panels, tidal and wave generators will benefit from HELIX results given the higher protection and safety of their supporting structures. On the other hand, the construction, heavy equipment, mining, aerospace and O&G industries, all being users of high strength corrosion resistant fasteners, are also expected to profit from the HELIX results.

HELIX results will be wrapped to elaborate industrial guidelines on the use of high dimension and high HE resistance fastener in OWT. Taking into account the HELIX technical advances, the knowledge gained in EHE cracking and the mentioned differences among standards, these guidelines will be used to influence on policy and practice in the offshore wind sector.

In summary, the following table details the progress beyond the state of the art to be carried out in the HELIX project:

Topic addressed in HELIX	Progress beyond the state of the art of fasteners for OWT
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<p>M64 fasteners with 12.9 properties</p>	<p>Presently, M64 (or larger metrics) fasteners with 12.9 steel grade quality are not produced due to risks of LME during hot-dip galvanizing or HE risk during service. HELIX will optimize high HE resistance 12.9 steel grade quality and zinc-flake base coatings able to hinder HE of the base steel. That will be a step forward for the realization of large offshore wind structures.</p>
<p>High corrosion resistant coatings without HE nor LME</p>	<p>Fasteners in the offshore industry are often hot dip galvanized. Hot dip galvanization produces a cathodic protective surface on the steel that can lead to HE or LME up to the point that it is not allowed for 12.9 steel grade. HELIX will develop high corrosion resistant coating achieving the required corrosion protection without the risk of HE and LME.</p>
<p>Knowledge of the effects of atmospheric corrosion on HE of HSS</p>	<p>It is still unclear how exposure conditions, material composition and microstructure, surface treatment and previous corrosion affect HE of HSS. There is even less knowledge about the effects of atmospheric corrosion conditions due to more demanding working conditions. HELIX will use advanced techniques such as in situ Scanning Kelvin Probe microscopy and Computed Tomography, as well as traditional techniques modified for improved sensitivity under both atmospheric and immersion conditions, to advance in the knowledge of hydrogen absorption and HE of HSS under atmospheric conditions.</p>
<p>Knowledge on the interaction of coating and HSS in atmospheric conditions and under cathodic protection</p>	<p>Coatings anodic to the substrate metal may lead to HE due to cathodic polarization of the metal in defects. HELIX will advance in the knowledge of the effect of different coating parameters on hydrogen absorption and HE, as well as corrosion protection. In particular, it will be investigated if steel corrosion protection by the cathodic effect of zinc flakes is inherently linked to increased risk of HE. HELIX will provide new insights into the mechanism behind both factors and identify properties controlling each of them. This knowledge will not only allow tailoring the coating microstructure to achieve both excellent corrosion protection ability and low risk of HE but also influence on policy and practice in the offshore wind sector.</p>

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